

ACADEMY OF SCIENCES OF THE
USSR

INSTITUTE OF SPECTROSCOPY

Preprint No. 1

A SYSTEM FOR THE AUTOMATIC PROCESSING
OF PHOTOSPECTROGRAMS.

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Troitsk - 1991

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ABSTRACT.

A system for the automatic processing of photospectrograms is described. The system includes a subsystem for scanning a photographic plate and inputting the data into a computer memory and a program package for processing the data with the purpose of obtaining the information about positions, wavelengths, wavenumbers, intensities, and profiles of spectral lines.

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1. INTRODUCTION.

The use of the photographic emulsion for recording spectra at grating spectrographs with high resolution and high dispersion is still the most widely used method for measuring spectral lines in atomic and molecular term analysis. A disadvantage of the photographic recording is that the data is not directly available for further processing, i.e. the plate has to be "measured" using a device generally known as a comparator or microdensitometer. The output from this procedure is a list of line positions, and it should also include a measure or at least estimate of the intensity of each line. The manual measurement of spectroscopic plates has always been a very time-consuming and demanding task, and many attempts have been made to facilitate the process and improve the quality of measurements [1-10]. The ideal solution is a fully automatic system where the photographic density along the plate is recorded, the lines are detected, and the line positions with characteristics of line profiles are determined. Nowadays a number of such systems has been designed and they are rather close to the ideal one [7, 10]. Our system for the automatic processing of photospectrograms is also one of the attempts to achieve this ideal.

2. HARDWARE CONFIGURATION.

The equipment of our processing system can be divided

into four parts (Fig. 1): an automatic microdensitometer 1 - 8, a laser interference transformer 9 - 11, a scanning-process controller 12, 13, and a computer 14.

Figure 1. The hardware configuration of the system: an automatic microdensitometer 1 - 8, a laser interference transformer 9 - 11, a scanning-process controller 12, 13, and a computer 14.

2.1. MICRODENSITOMETER.

The microdensitometer (Fig. 1) consists of a stand-frame 1, a two-coordinate sample table 2, two stepping motors 3 controlled by a motion control unit 4, two displacement meters 5, an illuminating unit 6, an optical-density measuring unit 7, and an analog-to-digital converter (ADC) 8.

2.1.1. THE SAMPLE TABLE AND ITS MOTION CONTROL.

The motion of the two-coordinate sample table 2 with an object 15 along each direction is realized by means of the stepping motor 3 driving a precision screw, which is coupled to the table through a ball nut. The displacements of the table in two directions are measured by two optical meters 5. Each of them consists of two transmission gratings, a lamp, and a detector element. The detector records the periodic change of transmission through the two gratings when one grating is moving with the plate table.

The automatic tracking system 4 places the table at a specified point with a high accuracy. The table begins his motion with a nominal speed but when the distance between the table and the final point becomes less then a definite value the speed decreases. The moment of the speed decreasing is defined automatically from the pre-set parameters which account the nominal speed of the table and its weight, and characteristics of the feed-back loop holding the table at the final point. The speed decreasing may be canceled by user's instruction for driver.

The microdensitometer may also be used in a hand-operated mode.

The main characteristics of the kinematic part of the microdensitometer are the following:

- (i) the dimensions of the operating space along the X and Y coordinates are 240×180 mm respectively;
- (ii) the accuracy of coordinate measurements is 1 μm ;
- (iii) the accuracy of table positioning is $\pm 4 \mu\text{m}$;
- (iv) the nominal speed of the table may be given from 0.2 mm/sec to 5.5 mm/sec;
- (v) the step of moving the table is 5 μm for the automatic mode and 0.7 μm for the hand-operated mode.

2.1.2. MEASURING THE OPTICAL DENSITY.

The arrangement for measuring the photographic density

consists of two parts: illuminating and projection-measuring ones. The illuminating part includes a lamp, a condenser system with a heat filter, a limiting aperture, and optical elements which project the image of the limiting aperture on a plate. The projection-measuring part includes an adjustable slit, optical elements for enlarging a small portion of the plate and focusing it in a plane containing the adjustable slit and in a plane of a screen, an adjusting compensation wedge for setting zero density, a photo-multiplier, a logarithmic amplifier, and an analog-to-digital converter. The optical scheme allows to have the following enlargements of a plate: 10 - 100.

The main characteristics of the optical-density measurement system of the microdensitometer are:

- (i) the optical-density range is 0 - 4 D;
- (ii) the limit of the root-mean-square deviation is 0.02 D;
- (iii) the quantification step is 0.01 D;
- (iv) the ADC has 12 bits resolution and the conversation time of 8 μ s.

2.2. LASER INTERFERENCE TRANSFORMER.

The laser interference transformer 9 - 11 is intended for obtaining interference signals in two channels and transforming it into information electric signals when the reflectors move up to 10 m with the speed up to 10 m/s.

The main characteristics of the transformer are:

- (i) the information representation is phasic;
- (ii) the sensitivity of output signals is $720/\lambda$ deg/ μ m, where $\lambda \approx 0.63$;
- (iii) the phasic long-time instability is less than 360 degrees within 8 hours;
- (iv) the mean frequency of output signals is 0.4 MHz.

The transformer in our system is used as follows. One channel is the so-called information channel, and the other one is the reference channel. The reflector 9 of the information channel is attached to the plate table in the X direction, and the reflector 10 of the reference channel is

attached to the objective of the microdensitometer projection unit (Fig. 1). The controlled value is the displacement of the table with respect to the objective.

2.3. SCANNING-PROCESS CONTROLLER.

The scanning-process controller consists of an electronic circuit 12 for the automatic control of the data flow and storing the data, and an electronic circuit 13 for the automatic checking the signals (Fig. 1). The data flow control implies the incessant phase-to-code conversion in two channels, the calculation of the table position relatively to the objective, reading the output data from the ADC 8, beginning from the specified position of the table and with the specified step along the X axis, and storing these optical-density samples in internal memory. Furthermore, this control must ensure the asynchronous reading to the computer of both optical-density samples from the internal memory and coordinates of the table. The control parameters set by user are coordinates of the first sample, a direction of the scan, and a scanning step. We have worked out a device which carries out all these operations [11]. The electronic unit 13 (Fig. 1) is intended for tolerance checking the output signals of the transformer 9 - 11. Such a checking has a great importance since for the reliable functioning of the measuring system it is necessary to check the speed of each reflector, relative speed of the table with respect to the objective, and, moreover, it is necessary to check the correctness of the laser interference transformer functioning and absence of the accidental discontinuous jamming and losses in signals. We have worked out an electronic device which carries out such a checking and detects the appearance of the mentioned jamming with a high reliability [12, 13].

The main characteristics of the scanning-process controller when using in the system of the automatic processing of photospectrograms are listed here:

- (1) the time mismatching of the coordinate measurements in the channels is less than $2.5 \mu\text{s}$;

- (ii) the period of forming the coordinate code in each of the channels and the code of relative coordinate of the table is 2.5 μ s;
- (iii) the scanning step is $2^{\text{step}} \times \lambda/2$, where step = 0 - 7, $\lambda \approx 0.63 \mu\text{m}$;
- (iv) the step accuracy is less than 0.05 μm .

2.4. THE SUBSYSTEM FOR SCANNING PHOTOSPECTROGRAMS.

The described above equipment controlled by a special program unit (driver) which is loaded to a computer constitutes the system for scanning photospectrograms, with the input parameters of the system being:

- (i) the nominal speed of the table;
- (ii) the name of the plate and the description of the spectrogram, which includes the maximum value of the optical density possible for this plate, the optical density of the veil on an unexposed part of the plate, and the contrast coefficient of the photoemulsion used;
- (iii) the number of scan sections, the distance along the Y axis between the sections, the coordinates of the first sample, the length of the passes, and the direction of the beginning of the scan;
- (iv) the description of the section which includes the number of passes for averaging, the scanning step and the instruction how to scan: in one direction or in both.

The result of functioning this system is a set of files united by the name of the plate. These files are input for the data processing system described below.

3. SOFTWARE.

The program package for processing the data obtained with the aid of the subsystem for scanning photospectrograms is designed for obtaining the most complete information about all spectral lines.

3.1. LOOKING THROUGH THE DATA.

Sometimes it is necessary to check the recorded data, look through the data as a three-dimensional picture including several sections, look through the data with their several derivatives, and so on. For these purposes a program unit, with the help of which the data of several files are simultaneously plotted onto the computer screen, plotter or printer has been designed. The scales in the X and Y directions and the first output points are to be specified for each used data file. Often it is desirable to get a display with solid lines between data-points. The display method (points or solid curve) is also specified for each file. The looking through process is then carried out frame by frame.

3.2. AVERAGING.

The data processing begins with the averaging of the passes in each section. At this stage we carry out a simple summation of readings from different passes and having the same X-positions. The obtained results are divided by the number of passes in the section. This averaging permits to diminish the noise resulted from the quantification error of the ADC and the noise added by the optical-density measuring system. Some of systematic shifts and deformations of the inputting image are also averaged by this means. These systematic shifts and deformations are resulted from (i) the finite measuring- and digitization time of optical density, (ii) the finite signal increasing/decreasing time in the measuring system, and (iii) deformations of the table and plate during the scanning process (especially when the table moves in different directions).

3.3. FILTERING.

To reduce the influence of the emulsion noise more

complicated filtering procedure which takes into account the spectral composition (spectrum of space frequencies) of the data must be used. We carry out the filtering procedure with the aid of a designed low-pass filter. To design such a filter the Fourier transform of a chosen portion of the data is performed and using the obtained evaluation of the spectral composition of the data one can choose the parameters of the filter. The detailed description of methods of filtering and filter design can be found in a number of publications [14-24]. We use the method of the so-called Nearly Equal Ripple Filter (NER) [23] as the most convenient one in our case (see App. A).

The fragment of a row spectrum (1024 points) and the result of the filtering procedure are given in Fig. 2, curves "a" and "b" respectively. The Fourier transform of the row spectrum is represented in Fig. 3 (logarithmic scale, arbitrary units), where the chosen parameters are shown: $\beta = 0.07$ is the band edge frequency; $\delta = 0.07$ is the transition band width. Figure 4 shows the curve on which $N_p + 1 = 33$ coefficients of the designed filter lie equidistantly: from b_0 at the beginning to b_{32} at the end of the curve.

3.4. DENSITY-TO-INTENSITY TRANSFORMATION.

We carry out the transformation of an optical density to a radiation intensity in accordance with the formula:

$$I = k \times (10^{D'} - 1)^{1/\gamma}, \quad D' = (D - D_0) \times D_{\max} / (D_{\max} - D_0),$$

where $D_{\max}$ is the maximum possible blackening of the photoemulsion used; D_0 is the value of the optical density of the veil on an unexposed part of the plate; D is the sample of the optical density; γ is the contrast coefficient of the photoemulsion used; k is the scale factor.

Figure 2. The fragment of a row spectrum (1024 points) and the result of the filtering procedure: curves "a" and "b" respectively.

3.5. SUBTRACTING THE BACKGROUND.

To calculate the intensities and positions of spectral lines as accurate as possible, it is necessary to evaluate and subtract the background. For this purpose we use the following procedure. Using a special editing program (to be described below) one can quickly move and look through the spectrum, choose fragments of the data which do not include data-points of spectral lines, and mark them. Then a special program unit accomplishes the algorithm of the spline regression with selection of data using the marked fragments (see App. B). The following parameters are set

Figure 3. The Fourier transform of the row spectrum (logarithmic scale, arbitrary units). The chosen parameters are shown: $\beta = 0.07$ is the band edge frequency; $\delta = 0.07$ is the transition band width.

for this program: the minimum and maximum numbers of breakpoints and the maximum number of data-points may be deleted. After the spline approximating the marked data, and hence the background, with the best quality is constructed, these spline and marked data are represented on the screen for viewing. Then the regression procedure is resumed with new parameters or/and data or the subtraction of the background approximation from the initial spectrum is performed.

Figure 4. The curve on which $N_p + 1 = 33$ coefficients of the designed filter lie equidistantly: from b_0 at the beginning to b_{32} at the end of the curve.

3.6. FINDING SPECTRAL LINES.

The finding of spectral lines is performed in our system by using the first and second derivatives of the spectrum [7, 10]. The derivatives are taken with simultaneous filtering for suppression the noise which increases when taking derivatives. For this purpose we use the method of the so-called Nearly Equal Ripple Derivative Filter (NERD) [23] (see App. A). The parameters β_1 and δ_1 of the filter are easily estimated either with the aid of the procedure described in Sect. 3.3 or by using the known β and δ from the filtering procedure and available

experience of working with single-type plates.

The peak of a spectral line is considered as the point where the first derivative is zero, the second derivative has a negative value, and there is a sufficient number of adjacent points on the left side or/and on the right side with the positive and negative first derivative respectively. For the more accurate determination of the first derivative zero-crossing the data-points of the derivative are fitted by a polynomial of optimal order. The second derivative is also used for the determination of the beginning and end points of the line profile for polynomial fit.

All found spectral lines are subdivided into three classes:

- (i) lines with one-side shape;
- (ii) asymmetrical lines whose positions are determined with the accuracy not better than digitization step (as also in the previous case);
- (iii) symmetrical lines whose positions are determined with the better accuracy as a zero-crossing of the fitted curve of the derivative data-points.

The output data of the line-finding procedure is the list of records, each containing the following information about one spectral line (Fig. 5):

- (i) the position of the line x^i ;
- (ii) the intensity of the line I^i ;
- (iii) the information about profile's points (left and right) with the maximum absolute value of the first derivative:

$$x^i - x_L^i, I_L^i, x_R^i - x^i, \text{ and } I_R^i;$$

- (iv) the information about profile's points (left and right) which lie on the level of $0.6 \times I^i$:

$$x^i - x_{LHW}^i \text{ and } x_{RHW}^i - x^i;$$

- (v) the additional information describing the class of the line, the existence of peaks of other spectral lines on the line segments

$$[x_{LHW}^i, x^i] \text{ and } [x^i, x_{RHW}^i],$$

and the type of deformation of the line profile: triangle or rectangle.

The analyzing parameters of asymmetry, with the help of which the classification of lines onto symmetrical and asymmetrical is performed, are the following:

$$(x^i - x_L^i)/(x_R^i - x^i), I_L^i/I_R^i, \\ (x^i - x_{LHW}^i)/(x_{RHW}^i - x^i), \text{ and } \text{ctg}(\varepsilon_L)/\text{ctg}(\varepsilon_R),$$

where $\text{ctg}(\varepsilon_L)$ and $\text{ctg}(\varepsilon_R)$ are the absolute values of the first derivative at the points where the second derivative is zero (see Fig. 5).

The setting parameters of the line-finding procedure are:

- (i) the minimum intensity of spectral lines;
- (ii) the minimum and maximum numbers of adjacent points on one side of the line profile;
- (iii) the parameters of maximum asymmetry of line classified as symmetrical.

3.7. EDITING.

The line finding technique which uses the derivatives produces accurate results when applied to simple isolated lines with well defined peaks and relatively symmetric profiles. For such lines locating the line position can be equated with finding the location of the peak. However, for asymmetric lines and for lines defined using one side of a profile this technique may only be used for detecting a line. For the more accurate determination of positions of such lines it is necessary to use special methods, such as the self-convolution, centroid, difference, and others [7]. Thus, for making up a list of line positions one needs the editing procedure which allows to use interactively either method for determining more accurately the position of a line. One of the most frequently used methods is the setting one, when a portion of the spectrum is displayed on

Figure 5. Each line profile is described by five points: (x^i, I^i) , (x_L^i, I_L^i) , (x_R^i, I_R^i) , $(x_{LHW}^i, 0.6 \cdot I^i)$, $(x_{RHW}^i, 0.6 \cdot I^i)$ and two angles: ϵ_L and ϵ_R .

a screen along with its mirror image reflected about a line mark in the center of the screen. The operator sets on a line by moving its direct image and so bringing two images into coincidence. The profiles of lines in this case are displayed as solid curves.

An information of two sorts takes part in the editing process: tables and graphic representation of data as points and curves. The process consists of viewing the spectrum with marks of the found spectral lines. A mark on the screen looks like a vertical line of some kind: solid, dotted or other, depending on the spectral-line profile characteristics obtained by the line finding algorithm.

There are two main regimes of the editing process: the regime of viewing the spectrum with the possibility of moving, pressing, and stretching the spectrum in the X and Y directions and the regime of looking over the spectral-line profiles. The viewing mode provides also the following options:

- (i) delete a mark or insert a mark to any place of the spectrum;
- (ii) display in addition to the available picture the current portion of the spectrum and its mirror image with respect to the screen center mark;
- (iii) move (press, stretch) the portion of the spectrum with appropriate changes in the mirror image in order to fulfil the bring-together (setting in other words) procedure;
- (iv) insert the mark at the point of the spectrum where the reflection mark is positioned on the moving portion of the spectrum;
- (v) invoke other procedures for working with the portion.

In the profile-looking-over mode the image of the spectrum is moved and subsequently positioned at the marks of the found spectral lines, with the current mark being superposed with the screen center mark. In addition, the current portion of the spectrum is displayed on a screen along with its mirror image, with the scale being suitable for the bring-together procedure. Moreover, the full information concerning the current line profile is displayed.

The user has either to agree with the proposed position of the spectral line, or to delete the current mark, or to carry out the bring-together procedure by moving the displayed portion of the spectrum. When operating with a line profile the following parameters are correspondingly changed:

$$x^i, x^i - x_{LHW}^i \text{ and } x_{RHW}^i - x^i.$$

Any line can also be commented and chosen as a standard line for the following procedure of calculating wavelengths

and wavenumbers (see below).

3.8. WAVELENGTH DETERMINATION.

When calculating wavelengths we use for the grating spectrographs of normal and grazing incidence the following relationships between the position of a spectral line on the plate and its wavelength:

$$\lambda = \frac{10^7}{M} (\sin(t) + \sin(s)), \quad \text{normal}$$

$$\lambda = \frac{10^7}{M} (\cos(s) - \cos(t)), \quad \text{grazing}$$

$$s = \pi\alpha/180, \quad t = x/\rho,$$

where ρ is the curvature radius of the grating in mm; M is the number of grating lines per mm; λ is the wavelength in Å; α is the angle in degrees (incidence or grazing angle respectively). Then we have

$$x = \rho \times \arcsin(M\lambda/10^7 - \sin(s)),$$

$$x = \rho \times \arccos(\cos(s) - M\lambda/10^7)$$

for normal and grazing incidence spectrographs respectively.

Really the grating equation curves, of course, differ from the cited ones, for example, because of the defects in the photographic-plate holders. Therefore, usually the so-called correction curve which allows for all such effects is determined.

The calculation of an evaluation of the correction curve begins with the selection of the spectral lines considered as standards and giving them the wavelengths and measurement errors of these wavelengths. Then, with the aid of the grating equation and given wavelengths the positions of the standards are calculated along with the deviations of these calculated positions from the measured ones. Using the method of the spline regression with selection of data (see App. B) the spline is constructed which approximates with the best quality the deviations of the standards from the grating curve and therefore is the approximation of the

correction curve. All used standards are weighted, with the weight of a standard line being calculated as a function of the wavelength measurement error and the line position measurement error derived from the parameters of the line profile. The minimum and maximum numbers of breakpoints and the maximum number of standards which may be excluded are set for the program code. After the best quality approximation spline is constructed, this spline and the standards are displayed on a screen for viewing in the axis: measured position - deviation, with the excluded standards being marked. The scale and rms deviation of the standards from the approximation curve are also given. At this stage it is possible to display in a text form the deviations of the standards from the approximation curve both in mm and in Å. Further, if the results of the approximation are satisfactory, the calculation of wavelengths and wavenumbers for the whole line list is performed using the grating equation and the approximation of the correction curve. If not, the regression procedure has to be restarted with new parameters or/and new data.

4. OPERATING CHARACTERISTICS OF THE SYSTEM.

In order to test the accuracy and reproduction of the line position measurements in our system we have made repeated scans of a blade edge with the step of $0.32 \mu\text{m}$ and the window on the plate of $1 \times 100 \mu\text{m}^2$. The time interval between the first and last scans has been of 10 min. Both the separate scans and the data resulted from averaging four scans in different directions (see Sect. 3.2) have been investigated. The data processing has been performed by the following way:

- (1) taking the first derivative with simultaneous filtering for suppression of the increasing noise;
- (2) finding the position of the profile obtained by taking derivative and looking like a spectral line, with the line being classified as symmetrical (see Sect. 3.6 and 3.7).

The results of the investigation are the following:

- (i) the half-width on the half-height of the line profiles was about $2 \mu\text{m}$;
- (ii) the reproduction of the line position measurements when using the data of scans in the same direction is $0.1 \mu\text{m}$;
- (iii) the systematic shift of two scans in opposite directions is $0.3 \mu\text{m}$;
- (iv) the reproduction of the line position measurements when using the data of the averaged scans is $0.1 \mu\text{m}$.

APPENDIX A

A.1. NEARLY EQUAL RIPPLE FILTER (NER).

The computational algorithm or filter for smoothing is represented as a procedure of the linear weighting of the input data. The weighting factors are the coefficients of the filter. Thus the smoothed output data y_n are calculated from the original input data x_n by the weighting:

$$y_n = \sum_{k=-N_p}^{N_p} b_k x_{n-k}, \quad (\text{A.1})$$

where b_k is the filter weighting coefficients; $2N_p$ is the width of the filter in samples; $2N_p + 1$ is the total number of terms in the filter. The output y_n is the convolution of the input x_n with the filter coefficient sequence $\{b_k\}$. The filter design problem consists then of determining a set of weighting factors $\{b_k\}$ giving the desired smoothing action.

It is well known that the weighting coefficients for the ideal smoothing filter of the band width β , $0 < \beta < 1$, can be directly determined from a Fourier series expansion of this ideal characteristic in terms of $\cos(\pi k \nu)$:

$$H_1(\nu) = \beta + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} 2b_k \cos(\pi k \nu), \quad (\text{A.2})$$

$$b_k = \sin(\beta k \pi) / (k \pi), \quad \nu = f / f_N,$$

where f_N is the Nyquist frequency or one-half of the sampling frequency. This expansion includes an infinite number of terms and as k increases the coefficients b_k decreases slowly approaching the limit $1/(k\pi)$.

In practice one can use only a finite number of terms and the first choice is to simply truncate the series after N terms. The disturbance effect of this truncation is the appearance of a slope of the frequency response function about the band edge frequency β and the variation about 0

and about 1. This undesirable rippling effect can be greatly reduced by altering slightly the truncated set of coefficients in an intelligent way [14-24].

The definitions of the significant filter parameters are shown in Fig. 6. For this method the approximation error ϵ , the transition band width δ , and the number of pairs of coefficients N_p are related by the useful empirical design formula [15, 17]:

$$N_p \approx (-20 \lg(\epsilon) - 7.95) / (28.72\delta). \quad (\text{A.3})$$

The effective passband width is $\beta - \delta/2$, as shown in Fig. 6, and it is assumed that $\delta < 2\beta$ and $\epsilon < 0.002$. It is more convenient to define the passband and stopband tolerance ϵ on a logarithmic scale in terms of dB as

$$\lambda = -20 \lg(\epsilon).$$

The design procedure then becomes

(1) Specify β , δ , λ and then calculate N_p from the Eq. (A.3) as follows:

$$K_r = \begin{cases} 0.13927(\lambda - 7.95) & \lambda > 21, \\ 1.8445 & \lambda < 21, \end{cases} \quad (\text{A.4})$$

$N_p =$ Integer part of $\{K_r / (2\delta) + 0.75\}$.

(2) For the given λ the window parameter η is determined as

$$\eta = \begin{cases} 0.1102(\lambda - 8.7) & \lambda > 50 \\ 0.5842(\lambda - 21)^{0.4} + 0.07886(\lambda - 21) & 21 < \lambda < 50 \\ 0.0 & \lambda < 21 \end{cases} \quad (\text{A.5})$$

(3) The filter coefficients b_k are then determined as

$$b_k = b_{-k} = \frac{\sin(\beta k \pi)}{k \pi} \times \left\{ \frac{I_0(\eta \sqrt{1 - (k/N_p)^2})}{I_0(\eta)} \right\}, \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, N_p, \quad (\text{A.6})$$

where $I_0(x)$ is the modified Bessel function and is easily

Figure 6. Definitions of β , δ , and ϵ used in design of nearly equal ripple (NER) filter.

computed from

$$I_{\omega}(x) = 1 + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left[\frac{(x/2)^k}{k!} \right]^2 \quad (\text{A.7})$$

The resulting filter will have a frequency response characteristic that is very nearly equal ripple about unity in the passband $0 < f < \beta - \delta/2$ and about zero in the stopband $\beta + \delta/2 < f < 1.0$.

For the unity gain at zero frequency the filter coefficients must each be multiplied by the factor

$$\left[b_0 + 2 \sum_{k=1}^N b_k \right]^{-1}, \quad b_0 = \beta. \quad (\text{A.8})$$

Having determined the filter coefficient sequence $\{b_k\}$ the calculation of the smoothed output then proceeds directly from

$$y_n = B(1)x_n + B(2)(x_{n+1} + x_{n-1}) + \dots + B(N_p+1)(x_{n+N_p} + x_{n-N_p}), \quad (\text{A.9})$$

where $B(k)$ is the array of filter coefficients with the correspondence

$$B(k) = b_{k-1} \text{ for } k = 1, 2, 3, \dots, N_p+1.$$

A.2. NEARLY EQUAL RIPPLE DERIVATIVE FILTER (NERD).

The same NER design method can be applied to the design of derivative filters. As is well known, the operation of taking the derivative of a signal that is embedded in noise is one that introduces additional noise. To minimize this effect a smoothing filter action is designed into the derivative filter. The ideal derivative-smoothing filter frequency characteristic is shown in Fig. 7 along with the tolerance scheme used.

The requirements of derivative action and a linear phase characteristic dictate that the general form of the filter be

$$y_n = \sum_{k=1-N_p}^N c_k x_{n-k}, \quad (\text{A.10})$$

where $c_k = -c_{1-k}$ for $k = 1, 2, \dots, N_p$.

The odd symmetry in the c_k is necessary for the derivative action and the even number of terms in the summation indicates that the output of the filter estimates the derivative midway between the sample points, i.e. with

Figure 7. Definitions of β , δ , and ϵ used in design of nearly equal ripple derivative (NERD) filter.

a half-sample delay. Thus the resulting filter is defined as

$$y_n = C(1)(x_{n-1} - x_n) + C(2)(x_{n-2} - x_{n+1}) + \dots \\ \dots + C(N_p)(x_{n-N_p} - x_{n+N_p-1}), \quad (A.11)$$

where $C(k)$ is array of filter coefficients and $C(k) = c_k$.

The first two steps of the filter design procedure are identical to the NER smoothing filter procedure, but the third step is the following:

(3) The filter coefficients c_k are determined as

$$c_k = -c_{1-k} = \frac{1}{m} \left\{ -\beta \cos(\beta m \pi) + \frac{\sin(\beta m \pi)}{m \pi} \right\} \times \left\{ \frac{I_0(\eta \times \sqrt{1 - (m/N_p)^2})}{I_0(\eta)} \right\}, \quad (\text{A.12})$$

where $m = (2k - 1)/2$, $k = 1, 2, \dots, N_p$.

The resulting filter will have a frequency response characteristic that has very nearly equal ripple about the unit slope line in the passband $0 < f < \beta - \delta/2$ and about zero in the stopband $\beta + \delta/2 < f < 1.0$.

For the exactly unity slope at zero frequency the filter coefficients must each be multiplied by the factor

$$\left[\sum_{k=1}^{N_p} (2k-1)c_k \right]^{-1}.$$

APPENDIX B

B.1. RECOVERY OF THE ONE-DIMENSIONAL REGRESSION WITH THE AID OF SPLINES.

One of the methods for evaluating a regression function is the construction of the cubic spline approximation of the function (the piecewise cubic polynomial approximation) with choosing the optimal number of breakpoints.

In order to explain what is the spline, let us break up the line segment $[a, b]$ into $(N + 1)$ pieces by a strictly increasing sequence of points $a_1 < \dots < a_N$ and denote $a_0 = a$, $a_{N+1} = b$. The function $\varphi(x)$ which on each interval (a_j, a_{j+1}) , $j = 0, \dots, N$, is described by the algebraic polynomial $P_j(x)$ of order m is referred to as a spline or a piecewise polynomial function of order m with N breakpoints at knots $a_1, \dots, a_N$. The coefficients of the polynomials $P_j(x)$ are in agreement with one another so that the conditions of continuity for function $\varphi(x)$ and its $(m - 1)$ derivatives at N breakpoints be satisfied, i.e.

$$\varphi^{(k)}(a_j - 0) = P_{j-1}^{(k)}(a_j) = P_j^{(k)}(a_j) = \varphi^{(k)}(a_j + 0), \\ j = 1, \dots, N, k = 0, \dots, m - 1.$$

Great amount of literature is devoted to general questions of splines and methods of the spline approximation [25-27]. We use for our purposes an algorithm of the spline regression (SR) when cubic splines ($m = 3$) with knots at equidistant points are constructed. The algorithm consists of the construction of the cubic splines with the different number of knots at equidistant points. Each of the splines minimizes the empirical-risk functional among cubic splines with the same knots. The spline for which the criterion (B.1) takes the minimum value is chosen. This corresponds to the construction of the cubic spline for which the empirical-risk functional takes the guaranteed minimum value. In addition, the construction of polynomials of order 0, 1, and 2 which are expressed in

terms of the cubic splines with the zero number of breakpoints is performed in the algorithm.

In the SR algorithm the empirical-risk functional looks as follows:

$$I(\alpha) = \frac{1}{l} \sum_{i=1}^l \left[y_i - \sum_{j=1}^{N+4} \alpha_j \mathcal{F}_j(x_i) \right]^2 / \sigma_i^2,$$

where $\mathcal{F}_j(x)$ are the fixed line independent cubic splines with knots at the points as the spline searched for. The definition of such splines - basis splines or B-splines - is given below.

The minimum of the empirical-risk functional is determined by solving the normal system of linear algebraic equations

$$S^T S \alpha = S^T y,$$

where

$\alpha = (\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_{N+4})^T$ is the unknown vector of coefficients of the cubic spline approximation of the regression function;

$y = (y_1, \dots, y_l)^T$ is the vector of the experimental values of the researching dependency;

$S = \{\mathcal{F}_j(x_i) / \sigma_i\}$ is the $l \times (N+4)$ matrix of values of B-splines at the experimental points x_i , $i = 1, \dots, l$;

σ_i^2 is the dispersion of the values y_i .

The spline approximation is expressed in terms of the solution of the normal system as

$$\varphi(x) = \sum_{j=1}^{N+4} \alpha_j^* \mathcal{F}_j(x).$$

where $\alpha^* = (S^T S)^{-1} S^T y$.

The value of the empirical-risk functional achieved when constructing this spline approximation is equal to

$$I(\alpha^*) = \frac{1}{l} \sum_{i=1}^l \left[y_i - \sum_{j=1}^{N+4} \alpha_j^* \mathcal{F}_j(x_i) \right]^2 / \sigma_i^2$$

and defines the quality of the approximation evaluated on the same sample on which this approximation is constructed.

The evaluation of quality of the constructed approximation which is valid for any random sample is given by the expression

$$J(N) = \frac{I(\alpha^*)}{1 - \sqrt{\frac{(N+4) \left[\ln \frac{l}{N+4} + 1 \right] - \ln(\eta)}{l}}} \quad (\text{B.1})$$

where $1 - \eta$ is the probability with which this evaluation is valid.

Expression (B.1) depends not only on the parameters α^* of the regression function but also on the number of knots N . When the evaluation $J(N)$ takes the minimum value the number N is said to be the optimal number of breakpoints of the cubic spline approximation.

When recovering the dependence using the sample of observations (y_i, x_i) , $i = 1, \dots, l$, it often appears to be useful to exclude some observations, i.e. to realize a selection of the sample. Using this method one succeed in constructing such a dependency on which the empirical-risk functional takes less guaranteed value then when using the whole sample.

The spline selection algorithm (SS) for the construction of the cubic spline approximation of the regression function with knots at equidistant points is defined by the following way. The m different pairs (y_i, x_i) are excluded in turn from the initial sample of the experimental data. Using the remained subsamples of the length $l - m$ the SR algorithm constructs approximations of the regression function (for each subsample there is his own approximation). The evaluation of quality which is valid with probability of $1 - \eta$ for all approximation functions is given by the expression

$$J(k_j) = \frac{I(\alpha^j)}{1 - \sqrt{\frac{(k_j+1) (\ln(1-m) - \ln(k_j+1) + 1) - \ln(\eta/C_l^m)}{1-m}}}$$

where k_j is the optimal number of degrees of freedom of the approximation function which is constructed on the j th subsample: $k_j = n_j + 4$ (n_j is the optimal number of knots of the approximating cubic spline); $I(\alpha^j)$ is the value of the empirical-risk functional achieved when making the construction of the regression function on the j th subsample.

Changing the number m of observations which may be excluded ($m = 0, 1, \dots$) the optimal number of excluded observations is searched for. This is defined by fulfilling the condition when the function $J(k_j)$ takes his minimum value when both m and j are variable. Under this condition the observations to be excluded are also defined.

For the effective organization of the selection process we do not carry out the full running over all combinations of the m removing observations ($m = 0, 1, \dots$), but use the modified algorithm. The first observation to be removed is that which has the largest discrepancy from the approximation function constructed on the whole sample. On each next step the observation which has the largest discrepancy from the approximation function constructed on the previous step is removed. The discrepancy of the observation (y, x) from the function $f(x)$ is considered as $(y - f(x))^2$.

B.2. DEFINITION OF BASIS CUBIC SPLINES.

A cubic spline with N knots can be represented in terms of basis cubic splines:

$$\mathcal{F}(x) = \sum_{j=1}^{N+4} \alpha_j \mathcal{F}_j(x).$$

The basis cubic splines are defined by the following rule. Suppose we have a line segment $[a, b]$ and a nondecreasing knot sequence having the length of N :

$$a = a_0 < a_1 < \dots < a_N < a_{N+1} = b.$$

The basis cubic spline $\mathcal{F}_i(x)$ is the cubic spline which

has zero values at each of the knots and at the ends of the line segment $[a, b]$, with its first derivative at the points a and b being equal to $+1$ and 0 respectively:

$$\mathcal{F}_1(a_i) = 0 \text{ for } i = 0, \dots, N + 1;$$

$$\mathcal{F}'_1(a + 0) = 1 \text{ and } \mathcal{F}'_1(b - 0) = 0.$$

The next $N + 2$ basis cubic splines have zero values at all knots except one knot where the value of the spline is equal to 1 . The first derivative of each spline at the ends of the line segment equals zero:

$$\mathcal{F}_j(a_i) = 0$$

for $i \neq j - 2, j = 2, \dots, N + 3, i = 0, \dots, N + 1;$

$$\mathcal{F}_{i+2}(a_i) = 1 \text{ for } i = 0, \dots, N + 1;$$

$$\mathcal{F}'_j(a + 0) = \mathcal{F}'_j(b - 0) = 0 \text{ for } j = 2, \dots, N + 3.$$

The basis cubic spline $\mathcal{F}_{N+4}(x)$ has zero values at each of the knots and at the ends of the line segment $[a, b]$, with its first derivative at the points a and b being equal to 0 and $+1$ respectively:

$$\mathcal{F}_{N+4}(a_i) = 0 \text{ for } i = 0, \dots, N + 1;$$

$$\mathcal{F}'_{N+4}(a + 0) = 0 \text{ and } \mathcal{F}'_{N+4}(b - 0) = 1.$$

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Подписано к печати 23.11.90 Тираж 100 экз.

Заказ № 512.

Офсетное производство 3-ей типографии изд. "Наука"